

Effect of temperature and substrate to biomass ratio on the conversion of organic matter into VFAs.

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Abstract

The production of volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from cheese whey was optimized. A central composite design (CCD) and response surface methodology (RSM) were used to design experiments and determine the individual and interactive effects of temperature and substrate to inoculum ratio on the conversion rate of VFAs. A decrease in substrate to inoculum ratio resulted in an increase of VFAs bioconversion. With regards to temperature, the highest bioconversion values were found at 28°C. This finding could have a high impact on the economy of the process due to the reduction of energy costs, as the usual temperature is 35°C.

Keywords

cheese whey; anaerobic digestion; volatile fatty acids; central composite design

INTRODUCTION

Cheese whey (CW) is a liquid by-product obtained from cheese production. It contains lactose, proteins, lipids, and salts (Asunis et al., 2019). CW is currently used for animal feed, biogas production, and to produce whey powder, lactose powder, or protein concentrate (Asunis et al., 2020). However, more sustainable solutions are needed to ensure the competitiveness of the dairy sector. The intermediate compounds of anaerobic digestion (i.e. volatile fatty acids (VFAs)) have a high added value, as VFAs are mostly produced by converting petrochemicals, with market values in the range of 450–2800 € per ton (Owusu-Agyeman et al., 2021). The accumulation and composition of the produced VFAs depend on several factors, such as pH, temperature, substrate composition, reactor design, organic loading rate, ratio substrate to inoculum, among others. Although in the last years research different types of substrates have been studied for VFAs production, more research is needed to maximize the conversion of organic matter to VFAs. The objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of the temperature and the ratio substrate to inoculum on the anaerobic fermentation of CW to produce VFAs under batch conditions. A central composite design followed by response surface methodology was applied to determine the effect of both parameters over the VFAs bioconversion rate.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Raw materials

CW was obtained from a cheese factory located in Palencia, Spain, where cheese is produced from pasteurized cow's milk. The total solid (TS) and volatile solid (VS) concentrations of CW were 60.3 ± 0.2 and 55.9 ± 0.4 g L⁻¹, respectively. The CW was frozen until used to avoid degradation. The anaerobic sludge (AS) used as inoculum was collected from the municipal wastewater treatment plant of Valladolid, Spain. The TS and VS contents of AS were 25.0 ± 0.7 and 15.1 ± 0.6 g L⁻¹, respectively. AS was stored at 4 °C until use.

Set-up

The selected factors for the study were the temperature and the substrate (So) to inoculum (Xo) ratio (So/Xo ratio), expressed as g VS g VS⁻¹. The selected range for temperature was 18-38 °C and the selected range for So/Xo ratio was 0.5-2.5. The experimental design is shown in Table 1. All the assays were carried out in duplicate, except for the central point (T9), which was repeated six times. The experiments were carried out in bottles with a total volume of 0.5 L. A volume of 0.1 L of AS was used as inoculum in each bottle. The corresponding amount of CW to keep the So/Xo ratio was added. Finally, distilled water was added up to a final volume of 0.2 L. Concentrated

sulfuric acid was used to adjust the initial pH to 5.5. Blank assays were performed to determine the VFAs production of the inoculum at the different conditions tested, containing only AS and water. After the set-up of each bottle, the headspace was flushed with N₂ to ensure anaerobic conditions. Then, the bottles were placed in an incubator at the correspondent temperature. The incubation time was 15 days. The volume of gas produced by the different substrates was calculated by measuring the pressure of the bottle's headspace. VFAs concentration and composition and pH were determined in the liquid fraction at the beginning and at the end of the assays.

VFAs bioconversion was calculated according to Equation (1):

$$\% \text{ VFAs bioconversion} = (\text{VFAs (g COD L}^{-1}\text{)})/(\text{VS in (g VS L}^{-1}\text{)}) * 100 \quad (1)$$

where VFAs and VS correspond to the concentration of VFAs at the end of the experiment and the initial VS concentration, respectively.

Table 1. Codified values, real values and response for VFAs bioconversion from CW.

Treatments	Codified values		Real values		Response
	Temperature (°C)	So/Xo ratio (g VS g VS ⁻¹)	Temperature (°C)	So/Xo ratio (g VS g VS ⁻¹)	Bioconversion (g VFAs-COD g VS initial ⁻¹)
T1	-1	1	20,93	2,21	10,92
T2	-1	-1	20,93	0,79	20,03
T3	1	1	35,07	2,21	5,83
T4	1	-1	35,07	0,79	86,67
T5	0	1,4142	28,00	2,50	6,98
T6	0	-1,4142	28,00	0,50	92,01
T7	-1,4142	0	18,00	1,50	12,66
T8	1,4142	0	38,00	1,50	14,84
T9	0	0	28,00	1,50	10,52

Central composite design

Central composite design (CCD) consists of a 2k factorial nucleus, six replications of the central point and 2k axial points, where k is the number of factors evaluated. Factorial design levels are codified from -1 to +1. Central point is replicated six times to estimate experimental errors. Axial points ensure design rotatability. The experimental design was analyzed using response surface methodology (RSM). All the evaluated levels were combined in nine different treatments. Codified and real values for both factors are presented in Table 1. For predicting the optimal point, a second order polynomial function was performed Eq. (2):

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_{11} X_1^2 + \beta_{22} X_2^2 + \beta_{12} X_1 X_2 + E \quad (2)$$

where Y represents the predicted response, β_0 , β_1 , β_2 , β_{11} , β_{22} and β_{12} are the regression coefficients. E is the standard error and X₁ and X₂ are the evaluated factors (Temperature and So/Xo ratio, respectively). Coefficient of determination (R²) was calculated to achieve the quality of fit to the model. The p-values of the parameter estimation were used to validate the model. P-values less than 0.05 indicate the significant model terms. Multiple regression analysis and the optimization process were performed using Excel software.

Chemical analyses

TS, VS and pH were performed in accordance with APHA (2005) Standard Methods. The concentrations of acetate, propionate, butyrate, isobutyrate, valerate, isovalerate, hexanoate, and

heptanoate were determined by using a gas chromatograph (Agilent 7890A, USA) equipped with a Teknokroma TRB-FFAP column of 30 m length and 0.25 mm i.d. followed by a flame ionization detector (FID). The carrier gas was helium (1 mL min⁻¹). The temperature of the detector and the injector was 280 °C. The oven temperature was set at 100 °C for 4 min, then increased to 155 °C for 2 min, and then to 210 °C. Total volatile fatty acids (VFAs) were calculated as the sum of these acids after applying the appropriate COD conversion factor.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental design data and the response obtained from experimentation (VFAs bioconversion) are presented in Table 1. The combination of factors in T4 and T6 resulted in the highest bioconversion of organic matter into VFAs, with values of 87 and 92% for T4 and T6, respectively. These rates are high when compared to previous studies, who reported VFAs bioconversions in the range of 55% (Molinuevo-Salces et al., 2024).

From the response surface plot (Fig. 1), it can be observed an increase in VFAs bioconversion with a decrease in So/Xo ratio and an increase in temperature. As said before, the highest values were achieved in treatments with low So/Xo ratio (T4, T6). On the contrary, treatments with high So/Xo ratios obtained low VFAs bioconversions in the range of 6 and 11%. (T1, T3, T5). Moreover, if T5, T6 and T9 are compared (all treatments at 28°C), it is proven that VFAs bioconversion increased as So/Xo ratio decreased. On the other hand, treatments with a constant So/Xo ratio of 1.5 performed at different temperatures (T7, T8 and T9) did not show a clear trend, indicating that temperature was probably not so determinant for high bioconversions. This finding should be highlighted since the reduction in the temperature of fermentation could have a high impact on the economy of the process due to the reduction of energy costs.

Figure 1. Response surface plot for VFA Bioconversion from CW.

Regression analyses for VFAs bioconversion percentage resulted in Eq.(3).

$$Y=10.52 + 8.09X_1 - 26.28X_2 + 1.42X_1^2 + 19.30X_2^2 - 17.93X_1X_2 \quad (3)$$

The R² coefficient showed that the model explained 94% of the variability data (Table 2). Eigenvalues were calculated resulting in values of k₁ = 46.03 and k₂ = -4.59, which indicated the presence of a saddle point in the plot surface. Therefore, the optimum for the evaluated response

was outside the experimental region evaluated, indicating that only the best operational point may be selected. Statistical analysis allowed us to set initial conditions and parameters to achieve best outputs for real-scale plant operation.

Table 2. Regression results for swine manure VFAs bioconversion from CW.

	VFA Bioconversion (%)	
	Coefficient	Prob
β_0	10,5	0,49
β_1	8,1	0,19
β_2	-26,3	0,01
β_{11}	1,4	0,87
β_{22}	19,3	0,09
β_{12}	-17,9	0,08
$R^2 = 0.94$, Adj. $R^2 = 0.85$, $F = 9,93$, Prob $F \leq 0,04$		
Error: Sum of squares = 8991 Mean Square = 1798		

Chemical composition of the VFAs is presented in Table 3. Acetic acid reached up to 70-77% of the total acids in treatments with high So/Xo ratios (T1, T3, T5) while butyric acid was the most abundant in treatments with low So/Xo ratios (T2, T4).

Table 3. VFAs composition for T1-T9.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of temperature and ratio substrate to inoculum on the bioconversion of organic matter to produce VFAs was studied by a factorial design of experiments. The ratio substrate to inoculum strongly influencing VFAs bioconversion rate. The effect of temperature was not so clear, obtaining the highest bioconversion values at 28°C, which could have a high impact on the economy of the process due to the reduction of energy costs.

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